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Reaction pathways and overpotential in the cathode

Project partners

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	Scionix Ltd.	Scionix
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
DFT	Density Functional Theory
IL	Ionic Liquid

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1. Introduction

Electrochemical reduction of solid sulfur (S_8 rings) into aluminum sulfide (Al_2S_3) is challenging due to multiple possible pathways. Reaction network is very complex as each reaction step have multiple possible intermediate species. The possible reaction network have a tree like structure with crossovers, due to common reaction intermediate between different reaction paths. The usage of unique ionic liquid electrolyte based on urea and aluminum chloride creates further complexity as the IL cations can coordinate with the sulfide poly-anions. Recent studies^[1,2] have indicated that the cathode redox reactions in Lithium-sulfur battery involve a reaction route $S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_6 \rightarrow Li_2S_4 \rightarrow Li_2S_2 \rightarrow Li_2S$ or $S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_8 \rightarrow Li_2S_4 \rightarrow Li_2S_2 \rightarrow Li_2S$. Similarly the favorable pathway needs to be identified for aluminum-sulfur battery system. Different pathways have varying thermodynamics for elementary steps, which in turn dictate the charging and discharge potentials observed. Quantum mechanical simulations based total energy and free energy estimations let us accurately identify most stable intermediates and thus the limiting potentials. The accuracy of the predictions made from such simulations can be directly tested through comparing the charge-discharge characteristics of the battery as well as via identification of semi-stable intermediates with spectroscopic characterization.

2. Computational Method

Density functional theory based electronic total energy calculation as well as finite temperature correction from heat capacity, zero point energy and entropy is evaluated with Amsterdam Density Functional package (ADF)^[3]. B3LYP hybrid functional and TZ2P basis set is used. For dispersion correction we have used the DFT-D3-BJ method as described in^[4]. To mimic the effects of molecular species in the electrolyte solution (considering the effects of dielectric of the media and solvation) a conductor like screening model COSMO is used^[5]. A dielectric constant of 15 and solvent molecules rigid sphere radius of 3.5 Å is used to model the typical ionic liquid electrolyte used in the project. All structures have been relaxed until the residual forces were below 0.002 eV/Å. In addition to the ground state structure, the vibrational modes are calculated using small perturbative displacements. Using these vibrational modes within a harmonic oscillator model, we estimate the finite temperature energy corrections at 400K.

Elementary reaction steps are electrochemical and the presence of electrolyte molecules and the electric field makes the estimation of the free energy change for electrochemical reaction steps a complex task. The computational hydrogen electrode (CHE) model allows us to approximate the reaction free energy of an electrochemical reaction^[6] at a certain applied potential from the reaction free energy calculated without the explicit consideration of the potential or the electrolyte. The model links the reaction free energy of each step that involves a coupled electron proton transfer to the applied potential by a simple linear relation of number of electron transferred times the applied potential in reversible hydrogen electrode scale. We have similarly defined an equivalent model for Al-

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battery with a reversible aluminum electrode scale for electrochemical potential evaluation.

This is our electrochemistry scale and free energy change is zero

To decide which pathway is active and the thermodynamic limitations in it (charge/discharge loss), we have taken a divide and conquer approach. For each two electron transfer step, free energy of solvated ions containing poly-sulfide chains are evaluated. For every step, the most stable species is considered as the reaction intermediate.

3. Results

Based on exiting understanding of cathode reaction mechanism in lithium sulfur batteries^[7-9], we explore plethora of polysulfide based ions, their formation reaction free energy for difference chain length and coordination. These results are summarized in table 1. We observe that the $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_x^-$ species is most likely to be formed.

Table 1: Relative Stability of S_x^- based ions/molecules

Reaction (Urea is/not involved)	X=8	X=6	X=4	X=2	X=1
	Energy in eV				
$\text{S}_x^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{Urea}^+ = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_x^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$	-6.51	-4.12	-4.02	-4.12	-4.75
$\text{S}_x^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{Urea}^+ = \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})\text{S}_x^-$	-4.42	-2.08	-2.02	-2.67	-3.79
$\text{S}_x^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{Urea}^+ + \text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- = \text{AlCl}(\text{Urea})\text{S}_x + 2\text{AlCl}_4^-$	-5.92	-3.32	-3.43	-3.60	-4.76
$\text{S}_x^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{Urea}^+ + 2\text{AlCl}_4^- = \text{AlCl}_3\text{S}_x^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+ + \text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^-$	-4.61	-2.39	-2.39	-2.82	-4.04
$\text{S}_x^- + \text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- = \text{AlCl}_3\text{S}_x^- + \text{AlCl}_4^-$	-3.38	-1.16	-1.15	-1.58	-2.81
$\text{S}_x^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_x^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$	-5.28	-2.89	-2.79	-2.89	-3.51

All possible reaction steps are also calculated free energy change at no applied potential in the reversible aluminum scale mentioned before. Sulfur is divalent and our elementary reactions steps involved simultaneous transfer of two electrons in each. The estimated free energy changes are as follows

- $\text{S}_8 + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -4.37 eV
- $\text{S}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2\text{e}^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.13 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -4.65 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_6^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -4.23 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2\text{e}^- = \text{Al}(\text{S}_4)_2^- + 4\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.40 eV

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- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.42 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_6^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.00 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -3.47 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -2.24 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -3.78 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+ + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}(\text{Urea})\text{S} + 4\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.79 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -2.54 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}(\text{Urea})\text{S} + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 3\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = \text{Al}_2\text{S}_3 + 6\text{AlCl}_4^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$ -3.07 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^- + 4\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = \text{Al}_2\text{S}_3 + 8\text{AlCl}_4^-$ -3.08 eV
- $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+ + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$ +1.23 eV

Based on these elementary step free energy evaluations, we propose that the most probable reaction mechanism is

- $\text{S}_8 + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^- + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}^- + 4\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2e^- = \text{Al}_2\text{S}_3 + 8\text{AlCl}_4^-$

Figure 1 portrays the consecutive reduction of S_8 rings into aluminum sulfide using atomic structure models

Figure 1: Grey, yellow and green spheres represent Al/S/Cl atoms. Arrows show the favored reaction pathway.

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Electrons transferred during each reaction steps are the carrier of energy as suggested from the linear correlation between free energy change and electric potential for each steps. For a reaction step, which is uphill, we need to provide driving potential to make free energy change non-negative so that the reaction step may go forward. This is the process during the charging cycle. For the overall charging reaction to go forward all the way to solid sulfur, each of the reaction step must at least be free energy neutral. Thus, the minimum charging potential is defined by the reaction step, which is steepest uphill. The charging potential at which this step is free energy neutral automatically ensures all other steps are forward direction as well. With this reaction mechanism, our estimate of this charging potential is 1.71 V.

On the other hand, we can drain energy (discharging) up to a potential such that no discharge reaction step becomes uphill in free energy. In essence, the reaction step with the smallest step defines the potential for discharge. At this potential makes one of the reaction step free energy change zero i.e. the discharge process cannot go forward at any higher potential although some of the reaction steps might still be significantly downhill in energy. For this proposed reaction mechanism, this potential is 1.12 V and the limiting reaction step is conversion of $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^-$

Into $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^-$ as shown in figure 2. Although experimental partners are, yet to test out this predicted charge and discharge potential, recent experimental work support these results^[10,11].

Figure 2: The reaction pathway thermodynamics at 0 V and 1.12 V discharge (reversible hydrogen electrode), at which potential one of the steps become free energy neutral limiting the discharge potential.

The presence of under-coordinated IL cation may allow a different reaction pathway to take place simultaneously

- $\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+ + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 3\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{S}_8 + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = \text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_8^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_4^- + 2\text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 2\text{e}^- = 2\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+ + 2\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2\text{e}^- = 2\text{AlCl}(\text{Urea})\text{S} + 4\text{AlCl}_4^-$
- $\text{AlCl}_2\text{S}_2^- + \text{AlCl}(\text{Urea})\text{S} + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})^+ + 3\text{Al}_2\text{Cl}_7^- + 2\text{e}^- = \text{Al}_2\text{S}_3 + 6\text{AlCl}_4^- + \text{AlCl}_2(\text{Urea})_2^+$

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4. Outlook

Our results must soon be compared to experimental cell testing as well as spectroscopic characterization of reaction intermediates made by holding the cell at different potentials.

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